

**Support Uptake Integrated
Pest Management and Low-
Risk Pesticide Use**

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Executive summary of the deliverable

The present deliverable (D5.1) constitutes the SUPPORT Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, due in M6. The deliverable aims to establish and outline a strategy for SUPPORT's communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Building on what was already agreed among partners in the drafting of the proposal, this document provides a further elaborated version and describes key tools, formats, channels and actions in detail, and indicates an action plan for activities to come.

WP5 has developed this deliverable and the WP5 leader (ARCADIA) has the main responsibility in leading and coordinating tasks related to communication and dissemination. However, these activities are largely depending on input from all consortium partners. Furthermore, ILVO is the leader of task 5.3 of WP5. The deliverable describes the relevant roles and responsibilities and sets out general principles of the project related to open science and data protection.

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
GA	The General Assembly
CA	Consortium Agreement
SC	Scientific Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Officer
PMT	The Project Management Team
EB	Executive Board (Core Team)
WP	The Work Package
WPL	The Work Package Leader
TL	Task leader
NCC	National Crop Cluster
CoP	Community of Practices
NoP	Network of Practices
PAB	Project Advisory Board
SCT	Scientific Coordination Team
DoA	Description of the action
SEC	SUPPORT Editorial Committee
SHP	Stakeholder Platform

1. Introduction

This document includes the SUPPORT project's **Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan**. The Grant Agreement (GA) establishes two official deliverables for this plan (the present document: D5.1 due M6, and an updated version: D5.2 due M24). In addition to these two deliverables, it may happen that changes or updates are introduced to the plan throughout the project's lifetime (e.g. components such as stakeholder mapping, action plan or our internal checklist may be updated and enriched). Such changes will be included in routine reporting.

The chapters of the present deliverable are listed as follows:

Chapter 2: Objectives related to communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results, briefly outlines the main objectives related to the tasks of WP5 and to the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Furthermore, the chapter sets out to distinguish between communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the context of Horizon Europe research projects.

Chapter 3: Communication and dissemination, presents the first key part of the plan, providing an overview of how communication and dissemination main activities will be articulated based on the targeted audience on one hand, and a general audience on the other hand. Tools, channels, and formats to be used are described.

Chapter 4: Exploitation of project results, is the second key part of the plan, focusing on exploitation activities aiming to make concrete use of the project's results.

Chapter 5: Plan of action and performance measures, outlines the various activities, the work packages involved, target audiences as well as performance measures applied.

Chapter 6: Management of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, refers to the different responsibilities of partners involved in these activities and the crucial role of the WP5 leader as a coordinator.

Chapter 7: Data protection and open science, sets out an overview regarding the SUPPORT project's approach in the context of data protection, communication, and Open Science principles.

2. Objectives related to communication, dissemination and exploitation of results

The below sections outline the objectives of WP5, as well as the objectives of the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. Furthermore, the similarities and distinctions of the three different concepts (dissemination, communication and exploitation) are explained.

2.1 Objectives of WP5

The EU-funded SUPPORT project will analyse the decision-making process to identify barriers and opportunities in the entire agrifood chain related to the adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM). On the basis of these results, the project will develop new strategies and policies enabling and supporting farmers and other stakeholders to apply IPM.

Within SUPPORT, the overall objective of WP5 is to ensure dissemination and optimal uptake of SUPPORT results. This will be done through a series of dedicated tools and sharing of information with all concerned actors (from pesticide users to the general public) identified through a detailed mapping. Furthermore, WP5 will support communication and dissemination activities at CoP's level and facilitate knowledge transfer and cross-pollination across CoPs in the NoP (see Section 3.2). Finally, WP5 will work to ensure a successful combination of stakeholder engagement (input) with a

dedicated communication and dissemination strategy (output) to fully exploit the results of the research.

2.2 Objectives of the plan

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are key to achieve the overall goals of the SUPPORT project and to maximise its impact. The present plan sets out a structured and systematic approach to plan, coordinate, monitor and assess all impact-related dissemination, communication and exploitation activities. In this framework, WP5 will coordinate project-wide activities and implement dissemination and exploitation measures to ensure that results meet real needs leading to a strong uptake. As noted, some components of the plan will be regularly reviewed and updated as necessary throughout the project lifetime, and a second version of the plan will be submitted in M24.

2.3 Distinction between communication, dissemination and exploitation

Communication, dissemination and exploitation are all part of any Horizon Europe project's legal obligations of the GA. While closely related, these three concepts differ from each other, and it seems important to briefly outline the differences for the purpose of this document¹:

- **Communication** relates to the promotion of activities and results of the project and aims to reach out to a wide range of audiences including citizens, media and different stakeholder groups. These activities take place from the start of the project until the end and aim to engage with specific stakeholders and experts of the field, but also to raise awareness, and be transparent, among the general public about the project activities and objectives, how public money is spent, and benefits of European collaborations. Communication activities include using various media channels to convey clear messages about the project. It should be noted that boundaries between communication and dissemination activities are sometimes blurred.
- **Dissemination** implies making the project results public and, through Open Science, disseminating knowledge and results for others to use (free of charge). The target audience is made up of different groups that may take an interest in the potential use of the results. Other scientists constitute a key target for these activities, however, also other stakeholder groups that can learn from the results can be important, including authorities, policy makers, food supply chain actors and civil society. Dissemination activities take place as soon as the project has any results to share, and may include publication of results on scientific magazines, scientific or targeted conferences, or databases. The aim of these activities is to boost the impact of the project, allow other researchers to benefit and build on the available results, contribute to the advancement of the state of the art in the field, and make scientific results a common good. As mentioned, boundaries between communication and dissemination activities are sometimes blurred. Therefore, these two activities are presented under one chapter in this document (see Chapter 3).
- **Exploitation** refers to making concrete use of results, be it for commercial, societal, environmental, or political purposes. The target audience for these activities include researchers, industry and SMEs, as well as relevant stakeholder groups such as authorities, policy makers, civil society, and others. Exploitation activities come towards the end of the project, when exploitable results become available, and go beyond the end of the project period. Activities include creating roadmaps to uptake, prototypes, software, as well as

¹ European Commission website, Horizon Europe, <https://rea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/Communication%2C%20Dissemination%20and%20%20Exploitation-2021.pdf>

sharing knowledge, skills and data obtained through the project. Outputs may include contributing to new legislation or policy recommendations. The aim of exploitation is to support innovation, the economy and society, as well as addressing a specific problem or responding to an existing demand.

SUPPORT aims to start mainly with communication activities, add the dissemination activities as results progress over the project lifetime, and then gradually increase both communication and dissemination activities. Exploitation activities on the other hand start at a later stage.

The figure below demonstrates these three streams and example activities that may be part of them.

Figure 1: Overview of communication, dissemination and exploitation streams

3. Communication and dissemination

The overall objective of communication and dissemination activities is firstly to promote the project and ensure its visibility. All the envisaged activities are focused, either directly or indirectly, towards the achievement of this objective. Promoting the project is crucial as it is a way of demonstrating how European research projects contribute to the knowledge diffusion across the international scientific community, and accounting for public spending by providing tangible evidence of the project's added value and benefits to society. Furthermore, communication and dissemination activities help to enable replicability and further use of the project results.

The below sections outline some of the key activities that set a crucial foundation for communication and dissemination, namely an established project identity, a thorough stakeholder mapping, main tools, channels and formats to be used throughout the project.

3.1 Project identity

Communication activities begin with the creation of the project's identity and public image to enable a wider engagement throughout the project.

Logo

The SUPPORT project logo consists of a green and blue circular symbol embedding a leaf, followed by the full project name written in capital letters. The font used is NorthCulture regular. The below images show the logo in its original colour (to the left) as well as a black and white version (to the right).

Figure 2: SUPPORT logo

Colours

The colours of the logo and the project identity are presented below.

Figure 3: SUPPORT colours and project identity

Templates

Templates aligned with the SUPPORT project identity have been developed. Annex 1 and 2 present the Word template to be used for the project deliverables (like the present document) and another Word template to be used for other project related documents and communications. Furthermore, the PowerPoint template to be used by project partners for presentations, is presented here below.

It can be noted that the fonts mainly used in the templates are Trebuchet MS (for headings) and Verdana (for text).

Figure 4: SUPPORT PowerPoint template (first page)

3.2 Audience and stakeholder mapping

The dissemination of knowledge from SUPPORT will be greatly facilitated by the multi-actor approach adopted in this project. A multi-step and multi-channel stakeholder engagement strategy has been designed to maximise the impact of engagement and dissemination activities, carefully tailoring materials and tools to the specific needs of the target audiences. Stakeholder activities will include both input (e.g. co-creation) and output activities (e.g. dissemination).

There are two levels of audience and stakeholder mapping. The first one relates to the establishment of National Crop Clusters and the Community of Practices, while the second one is a wider stakeholder mapping covering also other actors, areas and countries, establishing a Stakeholder Platform. The two levels of audience and stakeholder mapping are further described below.

Multi-actor approach - establishment of NCCs and CoPs

Through a multi-actor approach, SUPPORT will bring together a diversity of actors based on their knowledge, expertise and role in the society, for co-creation as well as for promoting and facilitating the use of project results.

- **25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs)** will gather a variety of actors in discussions aimed at identifying and developing future IPM scenarios and involving incumbent actors in co-elaboration of drivers and barriers. NCCs are a selection of cases covering a wide range of farm typologies, sectors and systems representative of the diversity of farming in the EU and associated countries. The NCCs include wheat, maize, onion, potato, strawberry, apple, wine grape and olive.
- In nine (9) of the NCCs, a **Community of Practices (CoP)** will be developed including public and private stakeholders (e.g. farmer associations, policy makers, retailers, advisors, researchers, supply-chain actors, consumers' and environmental associations). The involvement of CoP members in the co-production of results will ensure that results of the project match the needs and expectations of end end-users, citizens and civil society.

- A wider **Network of Practices (NoP)** will be the place for continuing dialogue with the surrounding socio-technical landscape as to create pressure to foster wider change. The NoP will also be used to communicate, discuss and disseminate results of the project with the entire community of stakeholders in the EU.

Establishment of the Stakeholder Platform (SHP)

SUPPORT findings and results will be packaged to reach, engage and address end-user needs and will be widely shared with all relevant actors. Resources will be mobilised to ensure that the project remains visible to society and that results are disseminated to all relevant targets outside of the consortium and CoP and NoP activities.

A Stakeholder Platform (SHP) will be established for this purpose. The SHP will consist of a list of contacts managed by the WP5 leader (ARCADIA), which will be used to disseminate information and invite relevant actors and the general public to events organised by SUPPORT and to keep them informed about the project's progress, activities and results.

To establish the SHP, a wider mapping will take place to identify as many relevant stakeholders and targets as possible in view of disseminating the results of the project as widely as possible. This mapping will include academic stakeholders, advisory services, technical institutes, regulatory bodies, farmer's union, but also media and the general public. The mapping activity is currently ongoing and consists in the following steps:

1. **WP5 establishes main and sub-categories of the stakeholder mapping**, based on the target groups outlined below, and circulates these categories in an excel document to consortium partners for input and validation. On national level the mapping has taken place for the CoP stakeholders, and they have been invited to participate in the national kick-off meetings. A complementary mapping is performed at the EU level with all other stakeholders not directly involved in the SUPPORT activities that take place at the national level.
2. **Once input from all partners has been received, the stakeholder categories are finalised by WP5.** Another round of consultations with all partners takes place, this time to identify stakeholders for the various categories at regional, national and EU level. At this point, partners are asked to focus on their countries/regions of expertise.
3. **WP5 finalises the mapping based on the input from partners.** As the listing will include names and contact details to stakeholders, the first priority will be to reach out to all stakeholders to inform them about SUPPORT and that they have been listed as potentially relevant stakeholders in the context of the project. The stakeholders will then be provided with the choice of opting out or remaining included in this listing. The SUPPORT project ensures that personal data processing and management comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provisions.
4. **The listing implies that stakeholders receive updates about the project activities and results such as events, newsletters or other communications**, and that they may also be contacted to participate in specific actions on a voluntary basis. Stakeholders are informed that they may opt out from the list at any point throughout the project lifetime.
5. **The final list will be kept on the project's internal SharePoint** to enable consortium partners to update the list and add any other stakeholders throughout the project period. As this list will be a dynamic document, a regular monitoring carried out by WP5 will be in place in order to keep track of new additions and inform them about the listing and provide them with the option of being included in the list or not.

Overview of key actors

While a thorough mapping of stakeholders and targets at an early stage of the project is crucial in order to initiate communication activities, it is important to note that additional stakeholders may be identified throughout the project. WP5 will collect information from partners to enrich the listing

and identify targets with the aim of further developing the dissemination plan and ensure a wide outreach of communication and dissemination activities.

The consortium has already identified a significant initial list of actors covering crop systems and IPM in the EU to ensure this approach. Such identification has been facilitated by the previous projects carried out by ARCADIA and other consortium partners. This has secured the identification of more than 400 European and national stakeholders having expertise and competences in IPM that will be added to our stakeholder database. Dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed to them in a tailored way and/or simultaneously to groups sharing the same interests. Relevant actors are grouped as follows:

Table 1: Key actors for communication and dissemination activities

Key actors for communication and dissemination activities	
Target groups (TGs)	Roles in the project
TG1: Scientific community and education	Scientific actors will be contacted to present our research results and new knowledge to the scientific community, all throughout the project. Such relations will also be used to comment on project approaches which may be used by SUPPORT consortium members to finetune their research approaches. Teachers and students are key end-users. As such, this community will help to continue disseminating SUPPORT results to future agricultural engineers who will use the results of the research after the completion of the project.
TG2: Farmers and/or their representatives (cooperatives and producers' organisations)	Farmers will have a concrete display of the project outcomes at CoPs level under real operational conditions. They will be encouraged to adopt IPM developments for broader application in Europe and other countries. Representative organisations play a crucial role in the project as they can provide technical advice to farmers and at the same time sell pesticides to the same producers. Communication and interaction with this group will help implement SUPPORT results at local and regional levels.
TG3: Advisors and extension services, incl. technical institutes or research centres for technical support	SUPPORT will provide this group with IPM novelties, and it will be encouraged to further adapt the results to local conditions or specific supply chains, whenever relevant. This group will be a multiplier of SUPPORT results with the objective that such local/regional dissemination will continue after the closure of the project.
TG4: Food supply actors, from processors to retailers	While not directly involved in pesticide use and IPM implementation, this group contributes to the overall objectives of reducing dependency on pesticide, through the development and implementation of private strategies and initiatives (e.g. zero pesticide schemes). They can promote pesticide free approaches to producers in vertically integrated sectors. Therefore, the SUPPORT results will help such groups of actors to further develop private schemes regarding IPM uptake and low-pesticide use.
TG5: Society and consumers	Key target groups in terms of dissemination, since one of the main objectives of SUPPORT is to improve public acceptance of products produced with low pesticide use. The group will be closely associated with the CoP dissemination activities and will also aim to raise public awareness of the challenges of the sector and the availability of new, more sustainable IPM techniques.
TG6: Policy makers and public bodies at regional level (RDP), national level and EU level	This group will be engaged in dissemination of SUPPORT results and in the stakeholder engagement as the consortium would like to discuss the policy recommendations and project deliverables with this group of actors. This group will be established in early days of the project to bridge research to policy in a concrete manner.

3.3 Tools and channels

The below sections provide an overview of the main tools and channels to be used for communication and dissemination activities in the SUPPORT project.

Website

The website will contribute to the communication and dissemination objectives of informing and raising awareness among target audiences and disseminating results. It is the core public communication channel of the project as it enables all stakeholders and the general public to follow the development of the project.

The website will consist in both static pages that will stay the same, and dynamic pages that will be updated regularly during the project period, including with videos, pictures, informative texts, public tools and deliverables when available. Information targeted to both stakeholders specialised in the field and to the general public will be published on the website and all content will be accessible to viewers without restriction. Furthermore, the website will enable visitors to sign up to newsletter and information send-outs, as well as to get in contact with the project partners in case of questions.

Figure 5: Website (example page)

Regarding the structure of the website, the “Home page” briefly introduces the project and provides hyperlinks to other key pages of the website through a menu that is placed at the left side of the page, such as project information, publications, latest news etc. (see figure 5 above). From this page, you can also use a search function as well as access the social media pages of SUPPORT through links/symbols provided. Furthermore, it is possible to subscribe to the project newsletter at the bottom right of the page.

When clicking on “**The Project**” in the menu, a sub-menu listing project summary, National Crop Clusters, goals and objectives, work packages, governance, partners, and links, becomes visible. These pages are briefly described below:

- **Project summary:** this page provides a full summary of the SUPPORT project, its motivations, objectives and main activities.
- **Goals and objectives:** this page further outlines the specific objectives of the project and its ambitions for the project period.
- **National Crop Clusters (NCCs):** this page explains the multi-actor approach which is the backbone of the SUPPORT research process and gives an overview of how the NCCs, CoPs and the NoP are connected to each other.
- **Work packages:** here, the 6 work packages are described, including the main objectives and activities of each WP.
- **Governance:** on this page, the management of the project is briefly outlined and the project coordination is presented. A special section is dedicated to the International Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (ISPAB).
- **Partners:** here, the logos of each of the consortium partners are presented. When placing the mouse over one logo, information about the organisation and a link to the organisation’s website become visible.
- **Links:** this page provides links to other projects and initiatives that are relevant or related to the objectives and activities of SUPPORT. This page will be updated regularly during the project period.

The other pages listed in the menu include the following:

Publications: this page will present the material resulting from the research activities of the project excluding confidential information. The page will be constantly updated with new material throughout the project, including formal documentation, scientific publications, articles, pictures, etc.

Medias: the media pages provide access to all material produced with the purpose of project communication and dissemination. Several sections are listed under media through a sub-menu including in the press, newsletters, communication toolkit, photo galleries and videos. These pages will be regularly updated throughout the project.

Events: information about upcoming events is available on this page, presenting key information regarding events relevant to the field and that may be of interest to SUPPORT partners and stakeholders, as well as events related to the project activities (e.g. workshops, trainings, conferences). This page will be regularly updated throughout the project.

Project data sharing: the project data sharing page is intended for the consortium partners aiming at collecting, storing and exchanging data, and will be further developed in the coming months. More details are provided in Deliverable 3.2: Data Management plan.

News: the news page includes any relevant news related to the project. This may include reports from recent events, information about upcoming events, publication of a newsletter or a new communication tool, or results from research activities. This page will be regularly updated throughout the project.

Contact us: a contact form is available on the "Contact us" page in case the website visitor would like to get in contact with the project coordination team. It will require the website visitor to enter personal data in order to submit a message to the SUPPORT project.

The website will be developed in WordPress, which will enable easy content management during the project and upon its completion. The SUPPORT website domain has been registered as: www.he-support.eu and will be launched mid-June 2023.

The website is developed and maintained by ARCADIA based on input and feedback from all consortium partners, and in particular the project coordinator.

In addition to the official project website, Wageningen (WR) has set up an internal Sharepoint and Teams channel for the consortium partners. It is the internal communication system of the project to enable exchange and communication within the consortium, share relevant information such as confidential deliverables, raw project results, etc., modify documents and disseminate results within the project.

Social media

SUPPORT will have a social media presence on Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube. The activities on social media will expand the outreach of the project, thus enabling communication of the project results to specific target groups and also encouraging responses and questions from these groups. The profiles have been set up and will be launched together with the website in Mid-June 2023.

Social media is a key component of any promotional effort. As soon as the social media profiles have been launched, all partners will be invited to follow them, and also to retweet and resend messages that are published. Active participation by partners in these channels will be important, including posting news, updates and relevant information with tags/labels to SUPPORT, but also retweeting and commenting on partners' and other stakeholders' comments and relevant messages related to the topics of SUPPORT. Another important factor regarding the social media activities will be to broadly use the trending hashtags linked with the topics addressed by the project. Posts and updates made by the consortium partners may be either in English or in their national languages.

The activities on social media will be maintained throughout the duration of the project and will provide project gains with good visibility in relevant LinkedIn groups and on Twitter. Regular posts will be produced to keep online communities interested and informed about SUPPORT activities, including public deliverables, scientific publications, details and news about trainings or events

organised in the context of the project, as well as other relevant facts worth bringing up to attract the targeted online community's attention. YouTube will be used to enable the target audience to access video content related to the project and its activities. Once published on YouTube, videos will be embedded to the official SUPPORT website and will also be shared on the other social media accounts.

ARCADIA is in charge of the core activities on social media, including creating the profiles and posting regular content based on input from other partners, as well as following existing relevant social media channels and groups. Consortium partners are encouraged to contribute by following the SUPPORT profiles on Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, as well as using the possibility to retweet and repost content from their organisations' channels using relevant hashtags.

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@SUPPORT_EU

LinkedIn: [supportIPM.EU](https://www.linkedin.com/company/supportipm.eu)

Twitter: [SUPPORTIPM_EU](https://twitter.com/SUPPORTIPM_EU)

Media relations

All partners will contribute to the project communication by sharing the materials and tools developed for this purpose with press contacts of their own regions and countries. The work package leader for WP5 (ARCADIA) will coordinate the partners in relation to when they should get in touch with press contacts and will provide partners with the written and audio-visual material, which the partners may need to translate and adapt according to their needs.

Exchange with other projects

SUPPORT will actively engage with projects on related initiatives (national and international R&I activities), specifically ongoing H2020 and Horizon Europe projects, and, in particular but not only, the EU-FarmBook project. To ensure synergy and collaboration between projects where possible, SUPPORT will prepare back-to-back project meetings, organise joint activities, workshops and common communication and dissemination activities. While WP6 (management and coordination) is leading this task, it will be done in collaboration with WP5.

Events

Different types of events make up an important channel for communication and dissemination. A sample of events that will be organised within the framework of SUPPORT are listed below.

- Main scientific findings and results of the project will be presented in **international meetings and congresses** with the aim to reach out to the scientific communities. In such events, specific sessions may be coordinated to increase the project's visibility.
- **Scientific workshops** will be organised, securing interdisciplinary research outside the NoP at the EU and international level.
- **Conferences for actors at national level** will be organised in national languages in order to communicate and transfer SUPPORT results to national actors not included in the CoP. Such events will include interactions with citizens and consumers.
- **Project workshops and events** will be organised to disseminate and exploit results for mutual learning and understanding (e.g. multi-actor co-creation workshops in WP3 and capacity building and co-creation workshops in WP5).
- **AGRI exhibitions and trade fairs** will be attended by SUPPORT partners to disseminate results and outputs.
- **Consortium networks** will be used for communication of project results and outcomes in specific events.
- **A final conference** will be organised at the end of the project to present all project results.

3.4 Formats

The main formats used for the communication and dissemination activities of SUPPORT are outlined in the sections below, including printed communication tools, practice abstracts, newsletters, scientific publications and others.

Printed communication tools

A communication toolkit will be developed, containing a leaflet, a poster and a concept note. The **leaflet** has the purpose of briefly presenting SUPPORT in an accessible way through both text and visuals, that may attract both the general audience and a more targeted audience. In a similar style, a **poster** is developed which may be used to present the project at events and conferences, providing an overview of the project highlighting key information. The **concept note** (see Annex 3) is aimed at the targeted audience with previous knowledge of the subject and outlines the key objectives and activities of the project, as well as the expected results and impacts. It can for example be used to introduce the project to stakeholders. All the communication tools will be made available through the project's website and SharePoint and may be printed and distributed at relevant events. Other printed material and tools might be developed during the project lifetime as needed, for example general presentations of the project, policy briefs, factsheets for farmers or specific material to be used at the occasion of the final conference.

In addition to the printed communication tools, SUPPORT will also produce **informative videos** that will be posted both on the website and on social media. A first video introducing the project has already been finalised and can be found on SUPPORT's YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/@SUPPORT_EU

Newsletters

Newsletters will be used to inform key stakeholders about the project's progress and results. Publications, events and activities that have taken place in previous months will be included, as well as relevant resources, links and in-depth information. Starting from M12, newsletters will be published biennially during the project and widely distributed. The newsletter will be sent out using a mailing list built on the wide stakeholder mapping and Stakeholder Platform and will also be available on the project website. The newsletter will be developed and sent out via a professional emailing solution (Mailjet). This tool also produces useful analytics and has easy-to-use mailing list management functions.

Practice abstracts

25-30 practice abstracts will be drafted using the EIP-AGRI format and published in English. The target audience for these practice abstracts will be the practitioners. The practice abstracts will be submitted in two sets in M24 and M48 and will be widely distributed e.g. through the EIP-AGRI website². The focus of the practice abstracts will be the SUPPORT innovations resulting from the project. Where relevant, consortium partners may translate the practice abstracts to other languages of their choice.

Policy briefs

Policy briefs will be produced targeting i) EC officers related to research and innovation, sciences, and policymakers; ii) national officers; and iii) regional officers/local authorities.

Press and news releases

Press and news releases will cover different specific issues and channels, in order to draw the stakeholders' and the public's attention towards the project. Press releases will be made before major events and sent to relevant media and will be used to communicate the project key milestones, trainings, events and any other initiatives which are worth bringing up to a selected

² EIP-AGRI website, <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format>

audience. News releases, on the other hand, have an informal structure of posts, are published on the website, and easily read by the public.

Existing networks and channels for communication will be used to maximise the impact and share SUPPORT's vision and results, for example through the EU-FarmBook project, blogs related to food systems and data economy, magazines and traditional media. In this context press and news releases will be an important tool.

Blog

Discussion groups in the form of sub-blogs fostering interaction and awareness raising, paving the way to WP4 and WP5 events and subsequent engagement with the CoP. Regular blog posts will be published and will be made available through the website.

Scientific publications

SUPPORT will contribute to sustainable agriculture and IPM research through the publication of scientific publications. Publications will range from scientific papers to articles in technical reviews. News about the release of scientific and peer-reviewed publications will be shared via the website and social media channels. Research papers will all be published as open access publications.

All publications resulting from the project will include a statement informing about the funding source, e.g. "this study was supported by the SUPPORT project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement number 101061028".

4. Exploitation of results

SUPPORT strives to share results and outputs of the project open access and free of charge. The dissemination and communication activities of the project will ensure to reach a wide range of farmers, advisors and extension services, policy makers at regional, national and EU level, supply chain actors and retailers, the scientific community, teachers and students and civil society. Such activities throughout the project will enable a strong uptake and exploitation of results towards the end of the project, and after the project's end.

4.1 Overall strategy

The SUPPORT research and innovation activities will result in an inventory of IPM tools including current and future tools; a monitoring system for a holistic assessment of current crop protection and IPM strategies; scientific reports and policy recommendations; IPM strategies and scenarios, as well as practice abstracts. Results of the project will be used for the improvement of crop production systems aiming for a reduction of dependency on pesticide use and climate change adaptation and mitigation.

At an early stage of the project (first year), WP5 will work with each partner to identify the exploitation plans and assess knowledge/capacity gaps or other elements that may prevent exploitation of certain results. This will be done through a questionnaire sent out to all partners, with short follow-up meetings as needed. Based on the answers received by the partners, a detailed plan will be prepared. A centralised, early planning of exploitation activities is considered to greatly enhance the impact achieved. This task will result in a detailed exploitation plan that will enrich this deliverable in the revised version due M48.

4.2 Exploitation routes

Exploitation routes to be explored for some of the foreseen exploitable results and assets are listed in the below table.

Table 2: Main exploitable results and assets

Main assets / results	IPR measures
Inventory of IPM tools with an overview of IPM measures, which will be classified as current or future tools and be grouped according to crop, pest group and availability	Copyright
Monitoring system for a holistic assessment of the impact of current crop protection versus IPM strategies	CC license
Scientific reports, reports and open data on understanding the performance, the role of farmers' behaviour and how policy factors and the socio-ecosystem lead to increased adoption of IPM	Copyright
Policy analysis, policy recommendations, policy toolbox and guide for policy design to provide a roadmap for effective transitions to IPM to achieve transformative change	Copyright
IPM strategies and future scenarios of 25 NCC	Copyright
Practice abstracts for each major SUPPORT innovation	Copyright

The main research results and assets of SUPPORT are expected to have a high exploitation potential. The overview below shows assets/results and the exploitation plan per target group. This plan will be further developed in the coming months based on the questionnaire to be sent out to all partners as mentioned in the previous section.

Table 3: Exploitation plan per target group

Target group	Assets	Exploitation plan
Scientific community and education	Monitoring systems, conceptual framework, scientific report, data and project methodologies.	To improve capacities for behavioural and experimental knowledge in research and education
Farmers and representative organisations	Practice abstracts and IPM strategies and future scenarios of 25 NCC	To exploit abstracts and strategies for farmers to make use of existing opportunities to increase the adoption of IPM and low pesticide input practices, to make their crop protection management more sustainable
Advisors and extension services	Inventory of IPM tools, IPM strategies and future scenarios of 25 NCC, practice abstracts for each major SUPPORT innovation	To improve the capacity of advisors and improved services by advisors and extensionists, to aid farmers in adopting IPM and low pesticide input practices and to encourage them to further adapt the results to local conditions or specific supply chains.
Food supply actors, from processors to retailers	Inventory of IPM tools, IPM strategies and future scenarios of 25 NCC, practice abstracts for each major SUPPORT innovation	Results will be exploited to further develop private schemes regarding IPM uptake and low-pesticide use, for the promotion of pesticide free approaches to producers in vertically integrated sectors.
Consumers	Project reports and publications, policy advice and recommendations.	To increase awareness of IPM and the consequences for their health and the environment, to improve public acceptance of products produced with low pesticide use and to raise public awareness of the challenges of the sector and the availability of new, more sustainable IPM techniques.
Policy makers	Monitoring system, policy options, advice, recommendations, a policy toolbox and a guide for policy design.	To inform policy makers about project results to design and implement policies to remove barriers and stimulate opportunities at farm system level and feed project results into EU policy networks.

5. Plan of action and performance measures

5.1 Performance measures

Measuring performance of communication and dissemination activities is of high importance and will include monitoring visitor traffic to the website, as well as visitors, followers and interactions on social media, uptake in press or media, number of participants at events/demonstration days and training sessions, number of publications, number of external contact requests, and number of stakeholders receiving the project newsletter.

Each consortium partner will be asked to report regularly to WP5 on communication activities carried out and give feedback on (i) targeted measures to promote the activity, (ii) target audience and number of participants, (iii) key messages formulated for each target group, (iv) what lessons have been learnt and/or what could be improved.

Presentations, videos, flyers, brochures and other materials developed and used will be presented on the SUPPORT website and shared among partners.

5.2 Plan of action

The table below outlines a plan of action related to communication and dissemination activities, and provides information about the actions planned, the WP in lead, as well as the target audiences and performance measures.

Table 4: Plan of action

Month	Actions	Lead	Audience	Performance measures
M6	Developing and launch of website	WP5	All	Visitors' views: 15,000, project links to 20 partners' websites
M12	Newsletters. Published biennially starting M12.	WP5	All	Publication of at least 6 newsletters. Distributed to at least 400 actors.
M6	Setting up and launch of social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)	WP5	All	3 social media channels, audience: 2,000, posts: 90, 3-5 hashtags
M6	Communication tools and material	WP5	All	Visual identity, 1 flyer and 1 poster, 1 concept note. Distributed to up to 3,000 actors.
M6-M40	Branding materials such as factsheets, presentations, project leaflets, informative videos, and promotional material	WP5	All	3 flyers, 5 factsheets translated to 8 languages, promotional material distributed to up to 3000 actors.
M6-M40	Multiplier campaign e.g. leveraging networks, blogs related to food systems and data economy, magazines and traditional media, to maximise impact and engage actors outside of consortium and identified target groups.	WP5	All (focus on policy makers)	8 Press releases, 10 interviews in radio/TV.
M12-M48	Blog	WP5	CoP	At least 20 blogposts
M48	Final conference	WP5	All	1 event, up to 300 participants
M6-M12	Stakeholder platform (SHP) establishment	WP5	All	1 SHP, up to 1,000 engaged actors, up to 12,000 actors reached

M6	SUPPORT Editorial Committee (SEC)	WP5	All	1 SEC
M40	Scientific publications and conferences	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	Researchers, students, teachers	10 scientific papers, 3 workshops with 100 researchers
M24, M48	Practice abstracts	WP5	Practitioners	25-30 practice abstracts
M12-M48	Specific conferences for actors at national level	WP3, WP4, WP5	All	16 workshops (2 per CoP)
M12-M48	Project workshops and events	WP3, WP4, WP5	All	10 capacity building workshops, 300 participants
M6-M48	Agri exhibitions and trade fairs	All	Business actors	Participation in up to 20 events
M12-M45	Policy briefs	WP3, WP5	Policy makers (EU, national, regional and local), researchers	5 policy briefs

5.3 Long-term sustainability and dissemination of project results

The dissemination and engagement activities that are part of SUPPORT aim to create a long-term sustainability ecosystem through regular collaborations and relationships among consortium partners and stakeholders will keep going also after the end of the project. Furthermore, the project sets out to take advantage of the stakeholder networks contacted during the project which will facilitate and support the continuous communication and dissemination among relevant groups after the completion of projects. In addition, the SUPPORT project website will be result-oriented towards the end of the project (compared to the project-centred approach at the beginning of the project) and will therefore be an interesting tool for end users. The project website will remain in place for at least five (5) years after the completion of the project to enable other stakeholders to build on SUPPORT tools for future newly developed tools and IPM packages.

6. Management of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

6.1 Tasks and responsibilities

ARCADIA is the WP5 leader and is thus responsible for the development and execution of the overall communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of SUPPORT, and most of the related activities. However, the work of WP5 is highly dependent on the input from all other work packages and partners as regards their separate activities, progress and results in order to provide a basis for content to communicate and disseminate. Furthermore, some of the partners are assigned as leaders for certain tasks and responsibilities within WP5, and some work packages are particularly connected to communication and dissemination activities (e.g. WP3 and WP4).

The table below outlines the main roles and responsibilities.

Table 5: Roles and responsibilities

Partner	Responsibility and involvement
WR (project coordinator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As project coordinator, WR is the primary interlocutor of ARCADIA on communication and dissemination activities and will be asked to validate the proposed Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WR will provide feedback and approval on communication and dissemination contents to be released on behalf of SUPPORT (where needed/requested). • As leader for WP6, WR is responsible for Task 6.4: Coordination on collaboration with related projects, which can also be considered as part of communication and dissemination activities.
ARCADIA (WP5 leader)	<p>WP5 leader for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, as well as task leader for all tasks under this work package excluding Task 5.3.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing, updating and implementing the present Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. • Defining key messages that will convey the objectives and goals of the project based on the perspectives of the project's target audience. • Developing SUPPORT logo, visual identity and various communication materials, e.g. leaflet, poster, newsletter. • Internal point of contact for all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities that will take place on behalf of SUPPORT. • Designing, updating and maintaining of the project website and social media profiles. • Producing content to be published on the website and external channels, newsletters and social media platforms, based on the active contribution of all partners. • Monitoring the impact and measuring performance of communication material and activities.
ILVO (task leader)	<p>ILVO is the task leader for Task 5.3: Coordination of the CoPs at NoP level for engagement and exploitation activities</p>
All consortium partners (see checklist in Annex 4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewing and validating the present Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. • Assisting ARCADIA by providing input needed to create the SUPPORT communication materials. • Sharing project information on their website, social media pages and newsletters. All their online tools should link to the SUPPORT website and social media pages. • Keeping ARCADIA informed as to relevant progress made by the project in their respective work packages, and any related communication activities and efforts, as well as information collected about their impact (incl. events, publications, news). • Assistance on drafting the EIP-AGRI practice abstracts as required. • Boosting presence of SUPPORT on social media. • All partners will promote the project to their own contacts and invite them to subscribe to the newsletter via the subscription form on the SUPPORT website.

6.2 Editorial Committee

A SUPPORT Editorial Committee (SEC) has been put in place to ensure quality and clarity of the various communication and dissemination tools of the project. While such committee is not consulted regarding each and every document (news, website), a consultation is organised where needed and in particular for certain key communication tools that are produced to last throughout the project (e.g. concept note, general presentation of the project, leaflet and poster).

The Committee is made up of one person per consortium organisation on a voluntary basis and is consulted mainly via email. Generally, WP5 initiates the process by sharing a semi-final document/tool, asking for feedback from the members of the Committee. Once feedback has been received by all, comments are taken into consideration by WP5 and the document/tool is revised as needed and finalised. In cases where required, the Editorial Committee may organise a meeting to discuss a specific tool/deliverable. Members of the Committee may also request to provide input on certain tools/documents, even in cases where this has not been initiated by WP5.

7. Data protection and Open Science

7.1 Data protection

SUPPORT ensures that personal data processing and management comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provisions.

For users from the EU viewing the website, a cookie banner will be displayed, providing a cookie policy and acquiring consent for the installation of cookies.

7.2 Open Science

Within the SUPPORT project, principles of the Horizon Europe Open Science will be implemented, referring to the scientific process based on cooperative work, tools and the diffusion of knowledge. All SUPPORT partners will follow methods and steps that assure the early and open sharing of the project outcomes. More specifically, pre-registrations of the research plans of the study implementation, as well as registered reports will be submitted to Open Access Repositories.

SUPPORT will manage research data and other research outputs responsibly, following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles, using a Data Management Plan and providing open access to research data via a trusted repository under the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

For further details about Open Science and SUPPORT's efforts to increase data re-use, please consult Deliverable 6.2: Data Management Plan.

8. References

EIP AGRI website, <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/eip-agri-common-format.html>

European Commission website, https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-dissemination-and-exploitation_en

ANNEX 1 - Template (deliverables)

Support Uptake Integrated
Pest Management and Low-
Risk Pesticide Use

Deliverable: [#]
Title: [name of deliverable]

Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme

Grant agreement: 101084527

Project duration: 48 months

Published by the SUPPORT consortium

Dissemination level: [text]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No. 101084527

Document Control Information

Project Title:	Support Uptake Integrated Pest Management and Low-Risk Pesticide Use
Acronym:	SUPPORT
Project Manager:	Dora Lakner
Scientific Coordinator:	Johan Bremmer

Deliverable	Number	[#]	Title	[Text]
Work Package	Number	[#]	Title	[Text]

Document Authors:	Name and organization		Contact first author:	
Contributors:	Name and organization			

Deliverable type:	[R – Document, report / DMP - Data Management Plan / OTHER]
Dissemination level:	[C-UE/EU-C - EU Classified / PU – Public]
Due date of deliverable:	
Actual submission date:	

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Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s)

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date

Document history

The Document Author is authorized to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarized in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in [insert relevant link to the sharepoint]

Executive summary of the deliverable

[Short summary of deliverable (objectives, approach and methods, teams involved, conclusions)]

Contents

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
GA	The General Assembly
CA	Consortium Agreement
SC	Scientific Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Officer
PMT	The Project Management Team
EB	Executive Board (Core Team)
WP	The Work Package
WPL	The Work Package Leader
TL	Task leader
NCC	National Crop Cluster
CoP	Community of Practices
NoP	Network of Practices
PAB	Project Advisory Board
SCT	Scientific Coordination Team
DoA	Description of the action

1. Introduction

Text

2. Approach

Text

3. Results

Text

a. Results 1

Text

b. Results 2

Text

4. Conclusions

Text

- Bullet points
- Bullet points

- xxx
- xxx

5. References (if relevant)

ANNEXES (if relevant)

Table 6: example

XXXX			
XXXXXX			
XXXXXX			

Table 7: example

XXX	XXX
XXX	
XXX	
XXX	

Figure 6: example

Source: XX

ANNEX 2 - Template (general Word template)

Title XX

1. Introduction

Text

2. Approach

Text

3. Results

Text

a. Results 1

Text

b. Results 2

Text

4. Conclusions

Table 8: xxx

xxx	xxx
xxx	
xxx	
xxx	

Figure 7: xxx

Source: xx

ANNEX 3 - Concept note

Concept note – SUPPORT

Length of project: 48 months

Project period: 01 January 2023 – 31 December 2026

Project coordinator: Stichting Wageningen Research (WUR), Netherlands

Consortium: 20 partners from 10 European countries (Denmark, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Spain, Switzerland)

The project

SUPPORT is a joint initiative of **20 organisations** from 10 different countries, including academia and higher education, SMEs, farmer cooperative organisations and public bodies. The project is funded under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme for a period of four years (January 2023-December 2026). With the main objective to pave the way for adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) tools and technologies, the SUPPORT project will develop relevant and actionable knowledge to be used in co-creation design with actors of public policies and private sector strategies. Through a project organisation of six different **work packages** and with a **consortium** that contains all necessary expertise and experience, SUPPORT will investigate why the adoption of IPM tools and low pesticide input practices is lagging behind and what could be done to address this situation.

Uptake of IPM tools in agriculture

To prevent and eradicate harmful organisms and thus secure crop yields, plant protection products play an important role in agriculture and in managing food production. However, existing crop protection strategies rely to a large extent on the use of chemical pesticides which may carry hazardous substances that can imply risks for human health, biodiversity and the environment. Therefore, there is a widely felt need to reduce the use of pesticides and to reduce the dependency of agricultural producers on the use of chemical pesticides. Nevertheless, this must be achieved without reducing food production, farm economic profitability and the provision of other ecosystem services.

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084527.

Well-designed integrated pest management programmes can play an important role to reduce the dependency on chemical pesticides. However, the uptake of IPM practices by farmers remains low today. We lack knowledge about the reasons why the gap between potential and realised uptake of IPM practices exists, and which pathways can bridge this gap.

Objectives and activities

The **specific objectives** of the project are the following:

1. To build a **SUPPORT Stakeholder Ecosystem** to co-create strategies and policies with actors.
2. To create an **inventory of current and future IPM tools** and assessment of their impacts on pest control efficacy, economic performance of farms and the environment.
3. To **identify barriers and drivers** in the entire agri-food system for the adoption of IPM and to analyse their role in farmer decision-making.
4. To propose **public policies and private sector strategies** for enhancing the adoption of IPM tools and technologies in a co-creation process with the engagement of relevant actors.

The project will create solutions by building on an **RRI (Responsible Research and Innovation) approach**, in particular referring to the analysis of the drivers and barriers in the external environment, which need to be matched with the understanding of the reasons why farmers and growers decide to apply IPM, low-risk pesticide use practices or rely on chemical pesticide use. This matching process will enable:

- A basis for the development of **strategies** to enable and **support individual farmers** to apply IPM and to make their crop protection management more sustainable.
- A basis for the development of **strategies** and policies at the **level of systems, landscape and rural areas** to remove barriers, to create new opportunities and to enable farmer systems to adopt IPM and low-risk pesticide use practices at a larger scale.
- A basis for the **adjustment of crop protection policies** at Member State and EU level.

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084527.

National Crop Clusters and Community of Practices

The development of the project activities takes place through the organisation of six work packages and in a co-creation process with stakeholders. A multi-actor approach will be the backbone of the research process as follows:

- **25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs)** will be used for data collection. NCCs are a selection of cases covering a wide range of farm typologies, sectors and systems representative of the diversity of farming in the EU and associated countries.
- In 9 of those NCCs, **Community of Practices (CoPs)** will be developed with public and private stakeholders to co-create strategies and policies.
- The CoPs will be embedded in a **Network of Practice (NoP)**, an overarching platform connecting all stakeholders.
- The NoP will be used to communicate, discuss and disseminate results of the SUPPORT project with the entire community of stakeholders in the EU.

The NCCs include **wheat, maize, onion, potato, strawberry, apple, wine grape and olive**. These crops were selected for their empirical diversity and suitability in studying the IPM techniques, barriers and drivers in different food sectors, with vastly different production methods and unique sustainability challenges. In identifying the NCCs, a balance has been sought between annual vs. perennial crops; specialty products vs. commodities; and a broad geographical spread in different climatic zones.

Country	Bio-geographical region	Perennial		Annual cropping system					
		Processing industry	Fresh	Wheat	Maize	Strawberry	Apple	Wine grape	Onion
Denmark	Continental						X	X	X
France	Continental								
Germany	Continental						X		X
Italy	Mediterranean		X	X					X
Netherlands	Atlantic			X	X				X
Belgium	Atlantic				X				X
Poland	Continental			X					X
Romania	Continental						X	X	
Spain	Mediterranean	X	X		X				
Switzerland	Alpine						X	X	
Greece	Mediterranean	X	X						

■ Mediterranean ■ Atlantic ■ Continental ■ Alpine X T4.3 Community of Practices 9 X T4.2 National Crop Clusters 25

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084527.

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The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084527.

ANNEX 4 - Checklist for partners

The active participation of all project partners is crucial for effective communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

This annex summarises necessary information and guidance for SUPPORT partners related to communication and dissemination.

Website and social media

- **Present SUPPORT on your institutional websites** and create links to the project website and social media (website: www.he-support.eu). Share project information and updates on your institution's website, newsletter or e-mailing.
- **Follow SUPPORT in social media** with your organisation's accounts and also with your private ones if you use them for work-related purposes:
 - **LinkedIn:** [supportIPM_EU](#)
 - **Twitter:** [SUPPORTIPM_EU](#)
 - **YouTube:** [SUPPORT_EU](#)
- **Share and react** when messages are posted on the SUPPORT accounts and use relevant hashtags: **#supportipm_eu #horizoneurope #ipm #sustainableagriculture**
- **Label or tag SUPPORT** when you post a message so that the communication team can detect and further disseminate the message.
- **Provide the WP5 leaders with social network addresses** of your organisation and, where relevant, your personal ones.
- **Review the information** offered about your institution on the website and suggest changes or updates as well.

Communication with WP5

- **Inform WP5 about your communication activities**, send them your news items and the collected media impacts. Respond in a timely way when WP5 requests an update on your communication activities.
- **Inform WP5 about publications** in peer-reviewed journals and send them a link to be shared on the website and shared on social media.
- When WP5 provides you with a **press release**, disseminate this in a suitable way and involve national or regional media when relevant/possible.
- **Document your participation in communication and dissemination activities.** Take some pictures and provide WP5 with a brief summary of the event and your participation. This way, WP5 will have sufficient resources to feed the website and social media and to comply with the requirements of the European Commission.

Disclaimers and templates

- Any **dissemination material or publication must indicate that the project received funding** from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme (see footer in the general Word template and PowerPoint template).

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084527.

- Example for publications: *This work was supported by the SUPPORT project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement number 101061028.*
- Example for other documents/communications: *The project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme of the European Union under grant agreement No 101061028.*
- Use the **common SUPPORT templates** for deliverables, the general Word template, and the PowerPoint template.
 - Templates can be found on the SharePoint:
https://wageningenur4.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/UPD_2021-06-29T15_29_22.8299787Z/External/WP5%20C.D.E/6.%20Templates?csf=1&web=1&e=K4wf68
- In case **other templates** are used, please make sure to include the funding disclaimer as well as the project and EU logo:
 - The **SUPPORT logo and the EU logo** can be found on the SharePoint:
https://wageningenur4.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/UPD_2021-06-29T15_29_22.8299787Z/External/WP5%20C.D.E/4.%20Logo?csf=1&web=1&e=psx4Ca

